

Title:

Roadmap and Challenges for Reinforcement Learning Control in Railway Virtual Coupling

Authors:

Giacomo Basile¹, Elena Napoletano¹, Alberto Petrillo¹, Stefania Santini¹

¹ Department of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy

Abstract:

The ever increasing demand in passenger and freight transportation is leading to the saturation of railway network capacity. Virtual Coupling (VC) has been proposed within the European Horizon 2020 Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking as a potential solution to address this problem. It allows to dynamically connect two or more trains in a single convoy, thus reducing headway between them. In this work, we investigate the main challenges related to the potential deployment of VC in railways. Its feasibility through Reinforcement Learning techniques is explored, discussing about technical implementation and performance issues. A qualitative analysis based on a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient control algorithm is proposed. The aim is to give a first insight towards the definition of a qualitative and technology roadmap which could lead to the deployment of artificial intelligence applications aiming at enhancing rail safety and automation.

Fundings and Disclaimer:

This research has received funding from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 881782 RAILS (Roadmaps for Artificial Intelligence (A.I.) integration in the rail Sector). The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Shift2Rail JU members other than the Union.

The information and views set out in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking. The JU does not guarantee the accuracy of the data included in this document. Neither the JU nor any person acting on the JU's behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Publication Notes:

This Journal Article is available in Open Access at:

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3183102>